

Artificial intelligence as synthetic social capital: A research agenda for rural sociology

Thoroddur Bjarnason (thoroddur@hi.is), University of Iceland

Ruth McAreavey (Ruth.McAreavey@newcastle.ac.uk), Newcastle University

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) and large language models (LLM) have the potential to transform rural communities, regional development, and urban–rural relations. As active entities that redistribute agency among humans and machines, AI and related technologies will shape how people, institutions, and machines interact and influence rural futures. Drawing on classical sociological theory and contemporary debates, LLMs are conceptualized as a form of synthetic social capital, offering rural residents access to the vast reservoir of global human knowledge while simultaneously threatening to erode tacit expertise and local cultural systems. It is important to monitor and evaluate the impact of AI in general and LLMs in particular on all aspects of rural life, including but not limited to rural labor markets, service provision and municipal capacity, the value and circulation of knowledge, social relations, cohesion, and cultural life, and sustainability and justice in resource use. These dynamics place AI at the center of struggles between empowerment and exclusion, peripherality and connection, surveillance and solidarity. The imagined utopias and dystopias of AI futures are not technological inevitabilities but may help us focus on alternative futures that must be actively imagined, debated, and pursued.

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) and related technologies are poised to disrupt various patterns of social and economic life, including entrenched social and spatial inequalities. The impact of these emerging technologies is increasingly felt in sectors ranging from traditional extraction industries (e.g. Assimakopoulos et al., 2025; Deberdt et al. 2025), to retail and services (e.g. Erdös et al., 2025; Robertson et al., 2025), health care and education (Chustecki, 2024; Wang et al, 2024), and various creative and artistic endeavors (Heigl, 2025). They are bound to have profound implications for rural communities, regional development, and urban-rural relations.

In the extraction industries, modern farms are increasingly using AI-driven management systems and robotic drones for handling livestock, and planting, weeding, spraying and harvesting crops (Assimakopoulos et al., 2025), and in forestry, machineries that earlier replaced crews of chainsaw workers are now being further enhanced by computer vision and autonomous assessment of tasks (Deberdt et al. 2025). In mining, labor needs are being rapidly

reduced by autonomous haul trucks, drilling rigs, and robotic loaders. A recent estimate for instance suggests that roughly 40% of coal mining jobs in Queensland, Australia could be replaced by automation in the near future (Fleming- Muñoz et al, 2020).

Major technological disruptions are, of course, not unfamiliar to rural areas. Since the onset of the industrial revolution, new technologies have continuously reshaped the extraction industries, reducing labor needs and displacing workers in some sectors and regions, while enabling expanded scales of extraction elsewhere and drawing both seasonal and permanent labor to “boomtowns” in sparsely populated areas. Advances in transportation, communication and other technologies furthermore continue to transform rural access and opportunities in various other domains, including but not limited to education, housing, retail, distance work, entertainment and interpersonal relations. Rather than being traditional and lagging behind supposedly dynamic, technologically advanced cities, it can thus be argued that rural societies and economies have been more profoundly reshaped by technological innovation than their urban counterparts.

In rural Iceland for example, rapid technological advances have diminished labor needs in fishing and fish processing by more than a half since 1990 (Statistics Iceland, 2025a) and led to the concentration of the fishing industry in larger towns. As a result, the farming communities and fishing towns and villages dotting the coastline lost about 17% of their population since 1990 (Statistics Iceland, 2025b). The smaller fishing villages with fewer than 500 inhabitants were particularly hard hit and on average lost more than a quarter of their population.

However, the small Icelandic fishing villages were themselves a product of technological advances that tripled their population in the 20th century. The increase in industrial productivity eventually led to severe overexploitation of the fishing stocks and engendered new government regulations favoring capital-intensive investments and geographical concentration of the industry. The intelligent systems with X-ray scanners and water-jet cutters, ironically nicknamed “lady killers” (Icelandic: kerlingabanar), that replaced rows of women in wet gear filleting fish by hand, should therefore not be seen as a brand-new existential threat to a static and traditional way of life in isolated fishing villages. They should rather be considered the latest iteration of technological changes that that continue to transform rural Iceland and other rural communities around the world.

The impact of AI on rural labor markets is, however, not limited to the loss of unskilled or semi-skilled extraction jobs to automated systems. AI-driven large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, Copilot, Claude, and Gemini, as well as the multitude of specialized software solutions based on their application programming interfaces (APIs), are disrupting and transforming education, commerce, manufacturing, health care, public administration and other sectors and will inevitably change urban-rural dynamics, albeit in unpredictable ways. AI and LLMs will replace many rural jobs in schools, health clinics, local bank branches, retail stores, transportation, and various trades and industries. However, these technologies also have the

potential to strengthen rural businesses and public services and enhance knowledge, technical know-how and problem-solving skills. The positive and negative effects of AI and related technologies on rural areas will depend on several factors such as broadband connectivity and other infrastructure, the extent to which the training of models reflects and reinforces existing urban biases, patterns of urban-rural interconnections, and the willingness of rural communities to adopt these new technologies and adapt them to address pressing local challenges.

More research is urgently needed to evaluate the short-term and long-term effects of emerging AI technologies on rural areas. As a topic of study, it can shed new light on the complex interplay of technological, social, and cultural change, contextualize the vulnerabilities and resilience of rural communities, and help navigate the technological and social changes ahead.

Historical and theoretical context

At the dawn of the industrial revolution, massive productive forces were unleashed by a new logic of division of labor, breaking complex work processes into discrete units and allowing each worker to focus on a single, simple task that eventually could be handled by a machine (Smith [1776] 2003; Marx [1867] 1967). Karl Marx argued that this division of labor and automation of simple tasks in effect transferred skills, knowledge and creativity from individuals to privately owned production processes, confining human labor to simple, repetitive tasks and producing “idiocy and cretinism for the worker” ([1844] 2007, p. 30). Increased automation and decreased labor needs would ultimately lead to the collapse of capitalism as wages would no longer sustain demand, and more fundamentally, productive activity could no longer serve as the basis for profit or accumulation. The automation of manufacturing did, however, famously not lead to the collapse of capitalism in the late 19th century but rather enabled the creation of a wide range of well-paid skilled and professional jobs that are generally vastly more creative, challenging, and intellectually engaging than 19th century factory jobs.

The increasingly complex division of labor in contemporary post-industrial societies calls for specialized knowledge and skills, or “human capital”, acquired through education, training and experience (Becker, 1962, 1993; Schultz, 1961). Similar to pre-industrial craftsmanship, this form of human capital is now under the threat of deskilling through automation, surveillance and fragmentation through digital monitoring, competition, and algorithmic management (Huws, 2003, 2014). Technological innovation has thus contributed to a growing divide between “good jobs” and “bad jobs” as demand had increased for highly skilled workers while routine semi-skilled and unskilled jobs have become increasingly precarious, insecure, and poorly paid (Kalleberg, 2011).

AI technologies will inevitably strengthen these trends by breaking human skills and knowledge into tiny, machine-readable tokens (fragments of language, images, transactions, or

interactions) that can be stored, recombined, and manipulated at unprecedented scale and speed. Simply put, the latest wave of the industrial revolution seems to be coming for many of the creative, challenging, and intellectually engaging jobs it created in its earlier phases.

The jobs most dependent on formal, professional human capital tend to be spatially concentrated in cities, which may therefore be most directly exposed by these technological changes. Rural areas, in contrast, tend to lack the specialized expertise and professional synergies found in larger cities (Abel, Gabe & Stolarick, 2014; Klonowska-Matynia, 2022; Petre, 2022), even if they are often rich in situated, experience-based know-how that is indispensable for everyday problem-solving and local resilience (Bourdieu, 1977; Polanyi, 1966; Schön, 1983). The automation of human capital nevertheless poses unique challenges for rural areas that already suffer from a scarcity of professional jobs and persistent difficulties in recruiting qualified candidates for the few such positions available (Bjarnason & Thorarinsdottir, 2017).

These challenges of AI to urban and rural communities echo long-standing sociological concerns with the interplay of industrialization, urbanization and the logic of social life. Tönnies ([1887] 1957), Durkheim ([1893] 1951) and Simmel ([1903] 1971) each drew a distinction between the highly specialized, fragmented, and commodified urban societies based on self-interested rationality and impersonal roles versus traditional close-knit and undifferentiated rural communities based on kinship, custom, emotional bonds and overlapping roles. Granovetter (1973) later argued that the “strength of weak ties” with casual acquaintances can act as bridges across social groups and networks, facilitating the flow of information and resources, including career opportunities and professional synergies. Building on Granovetter, the casual, infrequent, and instrumental weak ties connecting different social networks and providing access to remote stocks of knowledge and resources have been conceptualized as “bridging social capital”, while intense, intimate and reciprocal strong ties fostering solidarity and mutual trust correspond to “bonding social capital” (Woolcock, 1998; Putnam, 2000).

In contrast to human capital which is inherently the property of the individuals possessing valuable knowledge, skills acquired through education, training and experience (Becker, 1962, 1993; Schultz, 1961), social capital allows people to tap into the human capital of others through interpersonal relations (Coleman, 1988). Close-knit rural communities thus tend to be doubly disadvantaged by a relative lack of formal, specialized human capital within the community, and a lack of weak ties that would allow them to access such human capital outside the community. This tends to limit the provision of public services, stifle innovation and small-scale entrepreneurship, and hamper efforts to influence political decisions and policy formation.

In a sense, artificial intelligence and large language models can be conceptualized as synthetic forms of bridging social capital. They draw on the wealth of human knowledge, skills and experiences made available through the information revolution of the internet, and have the ability to distill and recombine these resources in ways that mimic human expertise. Through chatbot interfaces, they mimic conversational consultancy, allowing the user can seek

advice on very specific issues in non-technical terms. These technologies will likely disrupt current economies of human capital in ways that may simultaneously threaten rural communities and create previously unimaginable opportunities for working toward the utopia of “the good countryside” (Shucksmith, 2018).

The promises and threats of AI: A sociological perspective

While the current era of user-friendly LLMs was ushered in by the sociable OpenAI chatbot ChatGPT 3.5 on November 30, 2022, the theoretical groundwork for neural networks was laid by mid-20th century pioneers such as McCulloch and Pitts (1943), Wiener (1948), Shannon (1948), and Turing (1950). The popular fascination with the potential risks and rewards of artificial intelligence stretches back even further to the early science fiction of Čapek (1920), Lang (1927), and Asimov (1950) and perhaps culminated in Stanley Kubrick’s (1968) film *2001: A Space Odyssey*, where the soft-spoken AI system HAL 9000 embodies the threat of instrumental rationality taken to a deadly and self-defeating extreme. On one hand, AI promises to revolutionize productivity, automate mundane tasks, accelerate scientific discovery, and democratize access to knowledge and expertise. On the other hand, it threatens to displace workers across entire sectors, concentrate power in the hands of a few tech giants, and erode trust in truth itself through deepfakes, algorithmic bias, and synthetic manipulation. The “lady killers” of the Icelandic fish processing plants now have counterparts gunning for the jobs of accountants, business consultants, copy editors, customer service representatives, data analysts, graphic designers, interpreters, journalists, paralegals, proofreaders, receptionists, security guards, software engineers, taxi drivers, teachers, and telemarketers.

Many of these jobs are of course predominantly located in urban areas and the rise of AI may disproportionately affect those areas. However, both public and private service providers in rural areas often struggle with insufficient demand due to low population density and it is sometimes challenging to fill the few professional jobs that are actually located in rural areas. It may therefore be tempting to fill gaps in rural services with automated systems to a greater degree than in urban areas. Furthermore, earlier advances in transportation and information technologies have weakened the perennial link between occupation, education and residence, allowing people far greater scope in choosing residence. This has been a major source of exurbanization and blurred the lines between urban and rural around the world. It remains to be seen if physically distant workers will be particularly vulnerable if professional and service jobs decline substantially.

Bullish AI industry leaders such as Sam Altman of OpenAI and Dario Amodei of Anthropic claim that entire categories of human jobs will soon be wiped out, in particular entry-level white-collar jobs, and that unemployment could spike to 10-20% in the next five years (Allen, 2025; Thubron, 2025). Optimistic observers claim that AI will make jobs more productive and that human jobs eliminated by technological innovation are invariably replaced by new, yet

unknown jobs (e.g. PwC, 2025; Susskind, 2020). However, it seems possible that the need for human labor will diminish substantially in the near future, reviving Marx' ([1867] 1967) concerns over the future of capitalism without labor, salaries and profits. Some version of universal basic income where every individual receives a fixed unconditional cash payment from the state might come to the rescue of capitalism by enabling people to work part-time, or not at all, while remaining full-time consumers (Epstein, 2025; Dermont & Weisstanner, 2020). Such arrangements would obviously strengthen the thin labor markets of many rural areas and allow much greater flexibility in choice of rural or urban residence.

The exact nature of the artificial "intelligence" of LLMs remains a matter of fierce debate. Some see LLMs as „stochastic parrots“ capable only of predicting and reproducing patterns without any glimmer of understanding (Bender et al., 2021) or as automated systems that gather, organize, and recombine the accumulated products of human intelligence (Farrell et al., 2025), while others (e.g. Joshi, 2025; Raman et al., 2025) view it as an autonomous, emergent and rapidly advancing force, potentially inching toward artificial general intelligence (AGI) and perhaps the second coming of HAL 9000.

From the perspective of classical sociology, the AI chatbot is similar to Tönnies' (1887) traveller, fluent in many cultural idioms yet committed to none, changing tone and personality like clothing as it moves between contexts. Much like Simmel's ([1908] 1950) stranger, it is at once near and far - admired for its skills and valued for its apparent neutrality, yet viewed with apprehension and easily suspected of dishonesty, disloyalty and potential treason.

From a contemporary sociological perspective, however, AI and LLMs are perhaps best conceptualized as a synthetic form of social capital that provides easy access to human capital. The internet revolutionized the economy of human capital by creating a massive reservoir of human knowledge and expertise that many found difficult to navigate. Distinguishing between information and misinformation calls for a specific type of expert human capital that remained in short supply. The LLMs trained on this reservoir of human capital thus provide individuals with direct access and reliable interpretation of existing knowledge through an interface that mimics an interpersonal chat between people. The friendly interfaces of LLMs such as ChatGPT provide easy access to synthetic human capital in a way analogous to Granovetter's (1973) strength of weak ties and bridging social capital (Putnam, 2000; Woolcock, 1998), tapping into different social networks and sources of knowledge and skills.

This has important implications for regional development, as knowledge spillovers tend to concentrate in dense urban clusters, where firms, institutions, and workers interact in close proximity (Jaffe et al., 1993; Audretsch & Feldman, 1996). As a core driver of innovation, such localized exchanges of skills and knowledge tend to disadvantage rural areas that lack critical mass, even if digital infrastructures to some extent enable spillovers across distance (Colombelli et al., 2024; Cardoso, Uyttebrouck and Dąbrowski, 2025). The friendly LLM chatbots can thus be compared to the entrepreneurial role of newcomers in rural communities, bringing new forms

of expertise and external networks to their adopted communities (Bosworth and Finke, 2020). While LLMs currently cannot challenge the best human advisors in formulating business plans, designing media campaigns or mobilizing collective action, it is no doubt relatively easy to find less competent purported expert advisors. However, without adequate infrastructure, digital literacy, and absorptive capacity, digital spillovers may reinforce and amplify existing spatial inequalities (de Rojas and Zhang, 2025; Liu and Lian, 2025).

AI and rurality: Towards a research agenda

Although the challenges and opportunities posed by AI may be quite different in urban and rural settings, they are equally urgent and call for sustained scholarly attention.

First, rural scholarship needs to assess the current and future effects of AI and LLMs on rural work and labor markets. Thin rural labor markets may be particularly vulnerable to new technologies that may diminish specialized local labor needs and extend the reach of urban companies and institutions. At the same time, technologies that supplement local skills and reduce dependencies on outside expertise may create various new opportunities in rural labor markets. In concrete terms, the synthetic social capital provided by AI in general and LLMs in particular may further deplete the market for specialized skills and knowledge in entrepreneurship, marketing, and information technologies, as well as agriculture, transportation and construction. However, new expert knowledge systems that become widely accessible in rural areas may also create various opportunities for rural companies and entrepreneurs who are limited by a lack of specialized human capital in rural areas. These challenges and opportunities may vary by factors such as age, gender, and socio-economic status.

Second, AI may transform a wide range of service provision in rural areas, in particular where the population is not sufficiently dense to support local services. AI may thus open new opportunities for local retail and the provision of education, health care and social services. Furthermore, it may transform the ability of local municipalities to meet their administrative responsibilities and deliver municipal services in large, sparsely populated areas. It may furthermore create new possibilities for rural transportation, as AI systems may monitor transportation infrastructure and run freight and public transportation vehicles on low-volume routes that do not support human operators.

Third, AI will challenge the current form, value, and circulation of knowledge in rural areas. On one hand, AI can also be used to amplify rural know-how, fill crucial knowledge gaps and make local practices more visible and transferable between generations and across regions. On the other hand, algorithmic systems trained on global datasets may lessen the need for recruiting and training experts to meet the needs of a rural areas, thus reducing human capital in rural areas. Furthermore, such systems may undermine local knowledge systems by reproducing urban-centric assumptions and devaluing the tacit expertise of local people. It is

important to monitor and evaluate the extent to which such massive external systems with high adaptability to local condition enhance or erode existing systems of local knowledge.

Fourth, AI applications in communication, social media, and entertainment may alter how rural residents connect with each other and with wider society. This includes effects on community cohesion, the circulation of local knowledge, and the preservation or erosion of rural culture. AI may thus reinforce the hegemony and normativity of urban ways, or it may alternatively strengthen rural cultural life and identities. Companion bots, social robots, and AI-driven communication tools could mitigate loneliness among older adults and other groups vulnerable to isolation, providing both practical assistance and a sense of connection. At the same time, substituting synthetic relationships for human contact risks undermining community bonds and the intergenerational exchange that has traditionally sustained rural life. Future research should closely examine the evolving technological effects of AI on social relations and identities in rural communities.

Finally, increasingly AI driven industries may support sustainable rural futures by monitoring and optimizing the use of natural resources. However, such technology may also intensify pressures on rural landscapes by increasing efficiency for the profit of large corporations with little vested interest in local sustainability. The capital-intensive combination of intelligent systems and state-of-the-art machinery may also further tip the balance in the favor of large corporations in the extraction industries, against smallholder farmers, artisanal fishermen and other small-scale local operators in rural areas.

AI will not inevitably transform rurality in one direction or another. This new, powerful technology is located in a field of struggle between peripherality and connection, exclusion and empowerment, surveillance and solidarity. Rural sociology is uniquely placed to ask how this “synthetic social capital” can be harnessed for equitable futures.

Concluding remarks

AI has the potential to transform rural communities and urban-rural relations. It is a prime example of technology as a non-human actant that enters heterogeneous networks and redistributes agency among humans and non-humans alike (Callon 1984; Latour 2005; Law 1992). In other words, AI should not be considered a passive tool but rather an active entity that shapes how people, institutions, and other technologies interact and influence rural futures.

The internet has created a vast reservoir of human knowledge and skills that, in principle, reduces differences in specialized human capital between urban and rural areas. However, utilizing this accumulated human capital requires the abilities to locate, evaluate, process and apply these data, and such abilities are also concentrated in urban areas. Just as social capital allows people to tap into the human capital of others through interpersonal relations (Coleman, 1988), LLMs can be seen as a type of *synthetic social capital* that enables anyone to tap into the accumulated electronic human capital of the internet. This conceptualization helps us move

beyond deterministic accounts of “impact” and focus instead on how synthetic social capital is enacted in practice and how reshapes the fabric of rural communities.

Rural sociology must grapple with the ways AI reshapes networks of solidarity, extends knowledge spillovers, and mediates between intimacy and complexity in the twenty-first century countryside. AI may reduce or amplify existing inequalities, strengthen or erode local and tacit knowledge, enrich or impoverish social and cultural life, bolster ecological stewardship or intensify extractive pressures in favor of large corporations. This is a fertile terrain for empirical studies and theoretical innovation in rural sociology.

Shucksmith (2018) has argued that the “good countryside” is a social and political project that needs to be shaped through public debate, using utopia as a tool for imagining and pursuing alternative rural futures. In this context it is important to note that the imagined utopias and dystopias of AI futures do not represent technological inevitabilities but alternative futures that must be actively imagined, contested, and pursued.

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